

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Open Science assessment guide

Actionable version

Definition

Open Science (OS) refers to research practices that make scientific knowledge accessible, transparent, reusable, and inclusive. It covers open access to publications, open and FAIR data, open methodologies and software, open peer review, citizen science, and broader engagement with society. In the context of research assessment, OS-aware research assessment means valuing contributions beyond traditional journal articles, recognising data sharing, collaborative practices, teaching, mentoring, leadership, and other activities that support transparent and inclusive research.

Relevant SCOPE stages

This resource aligns most strongly with the early phases of the SCOPE Framework:

- Start with what you value.
- Context considerations: Adapt OS assessment practices to disciplinary norms, national policies, and institutional missions.
- Later phases (Options, Probe, Evaluate) remain important for piloting and refining implementation.

When and how to use

Use this guide when e.g.:

- Designing or updating recruitment, promotion, or tenure criteria.
- Reviewing grant, fellowship, or award applications.
- Developing institutional assessment policies aligned with e.g. ARRA, or UNESCO recommendations.

Guidance

- Integrate monitoring: Shift from output-only tracking to assessing processes, outcomes, and long-term impacts.
- Update HR and assessment forms to allow for OS contributions such as datasets, software, protocols, mentoring.
- Pilot new assessment approaches e.g. narrative CV, openness profile with evaluators and researchers.
- Identify relevant outputs and activities using open databases e.g. OpenAIRE, OpenAlex, BIP!Services.
- Broaden recognition: Value diverse outputs (datasets, software, preprints, protocols, non-English outputs).
- Recognise roles and activities: Teaching, mentoring, leadership, citizen science, outreach, and engagement.

- Adopt FAIR and PIDs: Encourage use of ORCID, DOIs, and open licensing for findability and reusability.
- Acknowledge practices: Reward openness, reproducibility, inclusivity, collaboration, and peer review.
- Ensure equity: Consider structural constraints e.g. costs of OA, disciplinary differences).
- Train assessors and researchers: Provide guidance on narrative CVs, responsible metrics, and OS tools.
- Use incentives: Offer recognition in promotion, salary bonuses, awards, or badges for OS practices.

Further reading

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

- Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525987>
- Guide on the diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526089>

Other

- European Commission (2019): Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Schomberg, R., Britt Holbrook, J., Oancea, A., Kamerlin, S. et al., Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/44528>
- Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA, 2022), CoARA, [The Agreement - CoARA](#)
- UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021), [Draft Recommendation on Open Educational Resources - UNESCO Digital Library](#)
- Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (2024), <https://barcelona-declaration.org/>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

